

The Influence of Letter Card Media on Learning Outcomes of Class 1 Students in Learning Theme 1 Myself Subtema 2 Me and New Friends at SDN 091277 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

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This research aims to determine the effect of letter card media on the learning outcomes of grade 1 students in learning theme 1 myself, sub-theme 2, me and my new friends at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate. The method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is pre-experimental type one group pretest-posttest. The population and sample used is saturated sampling with a sample of 22 people with two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, and the independent variable (y) in the form of letter card media. The data collection technique is the test technique. The test results using the T-test with the help of the SPSS version 21 program, based on the calculation results obtained $t_{count} = 22,906$ with a significance level (2-tailed) 0.000, significant probability < 0.005 , $t_{count} > t_{table} = 22.906 > 2.074$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of letter card media on the learning outcomes of class I students in the Sub-theme Me and New Friends at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a basic need for every human being that must be fulfilled throughout life. Therefore, education must be prioritized and prioritized by various parties such as the government, community, family and all stakeholders in the education sector. In addition, opportunities to get education are not only at school but also outside school. With awareness of the importance of education, it is hoped that all Indonesian citizens can get a decent education.

Oemar Hamalik (Bimawati, 2022:51) educational media are tools, methods, techniques, which are used in order to more effectively communicate and interact between teachers and students, in the education and learning process at school. This means that educational media is a combination of tools, methods and techniques used to make communication and interaction between teachers and students more effective.

According to Baharudin and Wahyuni (Kosilah and Septian, 2020:1141) learning is a change in behavior, a change in behavior from not knowing to knowing, from unskilled to skilled. This means that learning is a process in which behavior changes from not knowing to knowing or from unskilled to skilled

There are some students who cannot read. During the learning process, there are still many students who do not pay attention to the teacher when delivering learning material and are less enthusiastic about participating in the lesson. This is because teachers still use conventional media such as blackboards and textbooks, making learning only teacher-oriented. Apart from that, the use of learning media that is not yet varied also makes students feel bored and less active in class.

In the Indonesian language subject content, the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) set is 65. Based on the results of the Indonesian Language UTS in class I at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate, there were 19 students who got a score above the KKM (pass) and 3 students got a score below KKM (did not pass).

Based on the results of the PPKn UTS in class I at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate, there were 10 students whose scores were above the KKM (passed) and 12 students whose scores were below the KKM (did not pass). This shows that student learning outcomes in the Pancasila and Citizenship Education subjects are also relatively low because they do not meet the KKM. learning media is needed to improve student learning outcomes. One of the learning media that is very necessary is letter card media. Letter card media is a type of learning media that contains pictures and letters that can help students recognize letters and gain the ability to read simple words. Letter card media is a learning media that can be used to help students learn while playing. By using this media, students can learn in a more interactive and fun way, thereby increasing student interest and motivation to learn

Letter card media can be an effective learning medium in helping students understand the subject matter well, especially in learning theme 1 Myself, Subtheme 1 Me and New Friends. Letter cards are letters written on pieces of media such as cardboard, paper, board (triplex) and parts of the letters can be moved according to the wishes of the maker of syllables, words and sentences.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The thinking framework or conceptual framework is the process of answering the problem formulation based on the theory being tested, namely the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The conceptual framework aims to provide an overview of the basic concepts used in research so that it can show the flow of thought appropriately while being able to accommodate all existing problems by solving the problems.

Based on the results of observations that researchers carried out in class 1 at SD 091277 Siantar Estate, the problem was found that student learning outcomes in Indonesian and Civics subjects were still low. The reasons include, teachers still use conventional media (whiteboards), the use of learning media is not yet varied so students feel bored during the teaching and learning process.

In this research, researchers will use letter card learning media. To determine the effect of letter card learning media on student learning outcomes, this was done by giving an initial test (pretest) and a final test (posttest). Submission of the initial test and final test is carried out by providing questions related to the learning material. The initial test (pretest) is carried out before using letter card media in learning material, while the final test (posttest) is carried out after the learning process uses letter card media. From this description, the conceptual framework can be described as follows:

Chart 1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

METHOD

The research used is quantitative research. With a *pre-Experimental* Design type. Where the researcher used a One-group *Pretest-Posttest* Design. Quantitative is a research method in the form of data and numbers. According to Sugiyono (2020:16) Quantitative methods are called traditional methods, because this method has been used for a long time so it has become a tradition as a method for research.

Table 3.1 One Group *Pretest Posttest* Design

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
0 ₁	X	0 ₂

Information:

O_1 = *Pretest* before being given treatment or treatment

X = Treatment

O_2 = *Posttest* after being given treatment

The population in the research were all students at UPTD SD Negeri 19127 Siantar estate, and the sample taken by class I students was 22 students. This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the Normality Test, Homogeneity Test, and T-Test were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This research was carried out at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate which is located at Jalan Makmur, Rambung Merah, Siantar District, Simalungun Regency, from 27 September to 09 October 2023. This research was conducted to find out how much influence the letter card media has on student learning outcomes.

This research is a pre-experimental design research with a one group pretest posttest research design. Where students are given a pretest and posttest. The pretest is given before treatment, the aim is to determine the initial condition of the student before being given treatment. The posttest is given after the learning material is given using letter cards, the aim is to find out the final condition of the students given the treatment.

Instrument Trial Results

Researchers conducted trials on the question instrument in class I at SD Negeri 12357, Jl. Jati, North Siantar District, Pematang Siantar City, on September 27 2023. Where 22 students were given trials. Trials were carried out to determine validity and reliability as well as test the level of difficulty and differentiability of questions.

1. Validity Test

Validity is a measure that shows the levels of validity of an instrument. Validity was carried out using SPSS Version 26, a question item was said to be valid if the $r_{count} > r_{table}$ value, with a significance level of 5% or 0.05. In determining the r table, you can look at the r product moment table.

It can be seen that there are 20 valid questions, namely (question 1, question 2, question 3, question 4, question 5, question 6, question 7, question 8, question 9, question 10, question 11, question 13, question 14, question 16, question 18, question 19, question 20, question 21, question 22, question 23). Meanwhile, there were 5 invalid questions, namely (question 12, question 15, question 17, question 24, question 25). Valid questions can be used for the next test.

2. Reliability Test

The Cronbach's Alpha value obtained is 0.908, then this value is compared with the reliability coefficient criteria, namely if the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.7 then the questions are said to be reliable, so it can be concluded that $0.908 > 0.7$, so the questions on this test instrument are very reliable.

3. Difficulty Level Test

Shows that the 20 questions that were tried out were classified in the easy category, with 3 questions, namely (question 2, question 4, and question 5), 16 questions with a medium level of difficulty, namely (question 1, question 3, question 6, question 7, question 8, question 9, question 10, question 13, question 14, question 16,

question 18, question 19, question 20, question 21, question 22, question 23) and questions with a difficult level of difficulty of ` 1 question namely (question 1).

4. Differentiating Power Test

There is 1 question item which is categorized as very good, namely 3, namely (question 6, question 9, question 23), categorized as good, there are 12 questions, namely (question 2, question 4, question 5, question 7, question 10, question 11, question 13 , question 14, question 16, question 17, question 18, question 19), categorized as sufficient, there are 6 questions, namely (question 1, question 3, question 12, question, question 20, question 21, question 22, question 24), categorized There is 1 question item, namely (question 25) and it has a very bad category of 1, namely (question 15 cannot be used in the pretest and posttest).

Data Analysis

1. Normality Test

The Normality Test is carried out to determine whether the pretest and posttest data from the sample have a normal distribution or not. Normality test results using the Kolmogrov-Smimov method in the SPSS Version 26 program

Table 1 normality test

		Tests of Normality					
		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Class	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Hasil Belajar Siswa	Pretest	,167	22	,111	,903	22	,034
	Posttest	,170	22	,096	,924	22	,092

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

From the output of the One Sample Kolmogrov-Smirvow Test, it can be seen that there were 22 students . Sig (2-Tailed) shows the pretest value in the normality test, namely 0.111. Meanwhile, the posttest value for the normality test was 0.096. If the probability is > 0.05 , it means the data is said to be normal

2. Homogeneity Test

The Homogeneity Test is used to determine whether several population data variants are the same or not. The test was carried out with the help of SPSS version 26 For Windows. By testing criteria, if the significance value is > 0.05 , it can be said that the variance of the two data is the same

Table 2 homogeneity test
Test of Homogeneity of Variances

		Levene	df1	df2	Sig.
		Statistics			
Student learning outcomes	Based on Mean	2,707	1	42	,107
	Based on Median	2,113	1	42	,153
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	2,113	1	34,577	,155
	Based on trimmed mean	2,281	1	42	,138

From the results of the homogeneity test above, it can be seen that the significance value for the homogeneity test is 0.107. The significance criterion is > 0.05 ,

so it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest scores have the same homogeneous variance.

3. Hypothesis Test (T-Test)

In this study, a sample test was used to assess the influence of letter card media on learning outcomes in subtheme 1 Me and New Friends for class I students.

Table 3 t test
Paired Samples Test
Paired Differences

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper			
Pair Student 1 Learning Outcomes - Class	65,659	19,014	2,866	59,878	71,440	22,906	43	,000

obtained tcount = 22.906 with a significance level (2-tailed) 0.000, significant probability < 0.005, tcount > ttable = 22.906 > 2.074, so H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. This explanation shows that there is an influence of letter card media on the learning outcomes of class I students in the Sub-theme Me and New Friends at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate.

DISCUSSION

This research was carried out in class I at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate for the 2023/2024 academic year from 27 August - 07 October 2023. The population used was all class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate with a sample of 22 class I students.

In this section, the results found in the research that have been carried out will be described. The intended results are conclusions drawn based on the data collected and data analysis that has been carried out. This research aims to determine the effect of letter card media on learning outcomes in Subtheme 1. Me and my new friends, class 1 students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate, which has 22 students in this study. Before carrying out the research, the research first carried out instrument trials at the same level with different schools, namely at SDN 122357 Pematang Siantar. The trial was carried out in order to determine the number of questions out of 25 questions that would be tested in multiple choice form, namely 20 questions.

Based on the pretest results, the average student learning outcome score was 49.54 with all students scoring below the KKM. Looking at the existing percentages, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using letter card media was relatively low. Furthermore, the average score of the posttest results was 85.00. So after using letter card media students have better learning outcomes than before using letter card media. After carrying out the pretest and posttest normality tests, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.107 was obtained. Based on predetermined criteria, if the sig value is > 0.05, the data is said to have homogeneous variation. In this case it can be seen that 0.107 > 0.05. So it can be concluded that the data has the same characteristics or is homogeneous.

After the normality test and homogeneity test have been fulfilled, proceed to hypothesis testing. From the student test results, it was obtained that t_{count} was 22.906 and t_{table} was 2.074. Thus, $t_{count} > t_{table} = 22.906 > 2.074$, which means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is an influence of letter card media on the learning outcomes of class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate for the 2023/2024 academic year.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of research conducted on class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate for the 2023/2024 academic year. The data obtained can be concluded that in general the use of letter card media greatly influences the learning outcomes of class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate. The increase in learning outcomes can be seen from the increase in student learning outcomes which were initially measured before going through the learning process through the average of pretest activities, namely 49.54. After going through the learning process using letter cards as a medium, a posttest was given again to determine the students' final abilities, the average score increased to 85.00.

Based on hypothesis testing with a significance level = 0.05 and t table of 2.047. Thus $t_{count} > t_{table} 22.906 > 2.047$, it can be concluded that there is an influence of letter card media on learning outcomes in the sub-theme Me and New Friends for class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate. So based on the test results, the hypothesis H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which indicates that there is a significant influence of letter card media on learning outcomes in the sub-theme Me and New Friends for class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate.

Recommendations

From the research results, it is known that the influence of letter card media on the learning outcomes of my students and my new friends, class I students at SDN 091277 Siantar Estate for the 2023/2024 academic year, so the researchers provide the following suggestions:

1. For students, they can use media in this research as a way to develop students' abilities.
2. For teachers, they can use media in this research as an alternative way of learning to improve student learning outcomes.
3. For researchers, they can apply media in this research as an effort to improve student learning outcomes when they become teachers.
4. For schools, they can improve the media in this research on different materials or subjects

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